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ЖУРНАЛ ГЕПАТО-ГАСТРОЭНТЕРОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

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IMPROVEMENT OF TREATMENT METHODS OF IRRITABLE BOWEL SYNDROME IN CHILDREN

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ANNOTATION

Irritable bowel syndrome is a functional disorder of the gastrointestinal tract, the main manifestations of which are a violation of the act of defecation with pain syndrome in the absence of organic diseases of the colon. Objective: to improve treatment methods for children with irritable bowel syndrome. Material and methods of research. The case histories were studied and a clinical and bacteriological examination was conducted of 40 children from birth to 3 years old with irritable bowel syndrome admitted to the gastroenterology departments of the regional multidisciplinary children's center. Thus, complex treatment of children with irritable bowel syndrome, accompanied by intestinal dysbiosis and constipation, should begin with the use of the prebiotic Dufalac in combination with fermented milk mixtures, which help restore the intestinal microbiota and gastrointestinal tract functions.

Keywords: irritable bowel syndrome, treatment, children

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УЛУЧШЕНИЕ МЕТОДОВ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ СИНДРОМА РАЗДРАЖЕННОГО КИШЕЧНИКА У ДЕТЕЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Синдром раздраженного кишечника - это функциональные расстройства желудочно-кишечного тракта, основными проявлениями которого является нарушение акта дефекации с болевым синдромом при отсутствии органических заболеваний толстой кишки. Цель: улучшить методы лечения детей с синдромом раздражённого кишечника. Материал и методы исследования. Изучены истории болезни и проведено клинико-бактериологическое обследование 40 детей с рождения до 3-х лет с синдромом раздражённого кишечника, поступивших в отделения гастроэнтерологии областного многопрофильного детского центра. Таким образом, комплексное лечение детей с синдромом раздражённого кишечника, сопровождающегося кишечным дисбиозом и запорами, следует начинать с применения пребиотика Дюфалак в сочетании с кисломолочными смесями, которые способствуют восстановлению микрофлоры кишечника и функций желудочно-кишечного тракта.

Ключевые слова: синдром раздраженного кишечника, лечение, дети

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BOLALARDA ICHAK TA'SIRLANISH SINDROMINI DAVOLASH USULLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH

ANNOTATSIYA

Ichak ta'sirlanish sindromi oshqozon-ichak traktining funktsional buzilishi bo'lib, uning asosiy ko'rinishi yo'g'on ichakning organik kasalliklari bo'lmaganida og'riqli ichak harakatining buzilishidir. Maqsad: ichak ta'sirlanish sindromi bo'lgan bolalarni davolash usullarini takomillashtirish. Materiallar va tadqiqot usullari. Viloyat ko'p tarmoqli bolalar markazi gastroenterologiya bo'limiga yotqizilgan 40 nafar tug'ilgandan 3 yoshgacha bo'lgan ichak ta'sirlanish sindromi bilan og'riq bolalarning anamnezlari o'rganilib, klinik-bakteriologik tekshiruvdan o'tkazildi. Shunday qilib, ichak disbiozi va ich qotishi bilan kechadigan ichak ta'sirlanish sindromi bo'lgan bolalarni kompleks davolash ichak mikrobiotasini va oshqozon-ichak traktining funktsiyalarini tiklashga yordam beradigan fermentlangan sut aralashmalari bilan birgalikda prebiotik Duphalacni qo'llash bilan boshlanishi kerak.

Kalit so'zlar: ichak ta'sirlanish sindromi, davolash, bolalar

Relevance. One of the leading places in the structure of pathology of the digestive organs in children is occupied by functional disorders of the gastrointestinal tract, more often found among young children. With functional disorders, motor function, digestion and absorption of nutrients, the composition of the intestinal microflora and the activity of the immune system change in the absence of organic changes and metabolic abnormalities in the gastrointestinal tract. According to literary data, the causes of functional disorders are varied and often lie outside the affected organ and are due to a violation of the nervous and humoral regulation of the digestive tract [1,10, 12]. All this contributes to the development of dyskinetic disorders and the emergence of functional disorders, the issues of correction of which in children are important to this day [3,5,11] and remain an urgent problem for pediatricians. Their pathogenesis involves: disorders of neuroendocrine regulation, toxic effects, insufficiency of local blood circulation and factors leading to dystrophic changes in the glandular apparatus and integumentary epithelium [2]. According to the III Rome Consensus (2006), the main clinical symptoms of irritable bowel syndrome are recurrent abdominal pain or discomfort 3 days a month over the past 3 months, associated with two or more of the following signs: relief during defecation, onset associated with a change in stool frequency, onset associated with a change in the appearance of feces. Irritable bowel syndrome is a functional disorder of the motor and secretory function of the intestine, the main manifestations of which are a violation of the act of defecation, accompanied by pain in the absence of organic diseases, mainly of the colon without its structural changes. With irritable bowel syndrome, pain and discomfort in the abdomen are associated with a change in the frequency and nature of stool and a decrease in pain and discomfort after defecation. [4,6,8].

Three main factors play a role in the pathogenesis: a violation of the regulatory role of the central nervous system and the development of vegetative dysfunctions, disorders of the intestinal biocenosis, and motility disorders.

Functional disorders of the gastrointestinal tract, in particular, irritable bowel syndrome, accompanied by cramping abdominal pain due to intense contractions of the intestinal wall, diarrhea or constipation occur in almost all children, starting from the first months of life, and a number of authors consider them physiological [5,7,13].

Objective: to improve treatment methods for children with irritable bowel syndrome.

Material and methods of the study. The medical histories were studied and a clinical and bacteriological examination was conducted for 40 children from birth to 3 years of age with irritable bowel syndrome admitted to the gastroenterology departments of the regional multidisciplinary children's center. The clinical study was conducted according to the questionnaire. The qualitative and quantitative composition of the intestinal microbiota of sick children was studied in the bacteriological laboratory using the generally accepted method of stool culture developed by R.V. Epstein-Litvak and F.A. Vilshanskaya as modified by M.A. Akhtamova et al.

Isolation and identification of bifidobacteria was carried out according to the generally accepted research method, taking into account the degree of dilution of feces and the value of the inoculation dose. Diagnosis of microbial imbalance was carried out according to methodological recommendations. 20 children with irritable bowel syndrome received the prebiotic Dufalac in an age-appropriate dosage and fermented milk formulas (Group I), and the remaining 20 patients (Group II) received traditional therapy and adapted unleavened formulas.

Study results. The diagnostic criteria for IBS were: - recurrent abdominal pain or discomfort at least 3 days a month over the past 3 months, associated with two or more of the following: improvement after defecation; abnormal stool frequency (less than 3 times a week); abnormal stool form (lumpy/hard stool);

Additional symptoms were: straining during defecation; imperative urge or feeling of incomplete emptying, mucus discharge, rumbling and bloating.

In young children with irritable bowel syndrome admitted to hospital, the most common symptoms were alimentary constipation, which occurred due to the discrepancy between the volume and (or) composition of food and the physiological capabilities of the child. The study of the anamnesis showed that among the examined patients, 38-63.3% were on mixed feeding and 22-36.7% of children were on artificial feeding. The development of the disease was facilitated by: unfavorable obstetric history of the mother (24-40.0%), allergic reactions to food (14-23.3%), past intestinal infections (22-36.7%), helminthiasis (45-75.0%), hypoxic-ischemic changes in the nervous system (19-31.7%), suffered in utero or during childbirth. The anamnesis also revealed that 52-86.7% of children fell ill after a violation of the diet - a change in diet or food intake that did not correspond to the child's age in volume (24-40.0%) or composition (15-25.0%), carbohydrate abuse (sugar, chocolate), or lack of protein in food. In 25-41.7% of children, the cause of constipation was an unbalanced diet of the mother and in 8-13.3% - early transfer to artificial feeding.

Most patients had concomitant pathology: anemia in 51-85.0% of cases, rickets was diagnosed in 34-56.7% of patients, and every third child had signs of atopic dermatitis. Mothers of 53-88.3% of patients complained of periodic sudden anxiety and causeless crying of the child upon admission to the hospital, lasting about three hours a day for several days, 7-11.7% of patients had episodes of increased irritability or inconsolable crying ending without obvious reasons. Constipation was present in 43-71.7% of patients, regurgitation in 28-46.7% of cases, bloating in 39-65.0% of patients and anorexia in 18-30.0% of children. Increased frequency of stool, occurring with the onset of an attack of pain, was noted in 17-28.3% of cases, mucus discharge with feces was present in 11-18.3% of children. All observed children had a combination of symptoms of various types of dysfunction. Paroxysmal cramping pains associated with food intake were reported by mothers of 23-38.3% of patients, associated with defecation - in 13-21.7% of cases. Localized around the navel morning pain periodically occurring after waking up the child was noted in 19-31.7% of children. In all patients, when studying the intestinal microbiota of children, a deficiency of bifidoflora was revealed: in 20-33.3% of cases, bifidobacteria were cultured in 5.1×10^7 and in 40-66.7% of children - in 2.3×10^8 dilution. Bifidoflora in 9-15% of children in group I was determined in 3.6×10^7 dilution, in 21-35% of patients - in 1.2×10^8 , and in patients in group II - in 11-18.3% of cases their level was 1.5×10^7 and in 19-31.7% of patients it was determined in 1.1×10^8 dilution.

Sick children received Duphalac as a drug therapy aimed at eliminating the symptoms of gastrointestinal dysfunction.

Nursing mothers whose children were on mixed feeding were given a dietary correction with the exclusion of products that cause gas formation, it was recommended to raise the baby's head after feeding, avoid overfeeding the child and massage the abdomen clockwise before feeding. To normalize the activity of the gastrointestinal tract, eliminate constipation and intestinal imbalance, prebiotic Dufalac and diet

therapy with fermented milk mixtures were recommended in the complex treatment of sick patients of group I.

The basis for their appointment was that they are absorbed faster, are easily digested, normalize intestinal motility, promote the growth of bifido- and lactobacilli. It is known that the restoration of intestinal microflora is carried out with the help of eubiotics. The choice of a drug for the correction of dysbiotic disorders is a difficult task for a pediatrician. The most optimal choice for the step-by-step correction of dysbiotic disorders is a combination of pro- and prebiotics. The role of prebiotics - food ingredients that promote selective stimulation of growth and metabolic activity of bacteria living in the large intestine with high adsorption capacity, to have a beneficial effect, improve the health of the macroorganism by selectively stimulating the growth or metabolic activity of one or more strains of bacteria living in the large intestine (dietary fiber, Duphalac containing lactulose, etc.). Prebiotics are utilized by the microflora of the large intestine, which promotes the growth of bifidobacteria and lactobacilli, changing the pH of the environment in the large intestine. As a result of using the prebiotic Duphalac and fermented milk mixtures in children of the 1st group, flatulence disappeared the next day, and by the end of the 2nd day -

abdominal pain, the general condition improved in 49-81.7% of patients. By the end of the 3rd day, the stool of the 1st group of patients returned to normal and became regular. In the II group, bloating, constipation and bifidoflora deficiency persisted for 1.2 bed days longer.

The number of bifidobacteria increased by 1-2 orders of magnitude in all examined patients. Bifidoflora in 19-31.7% of children in the I group who received Dufalac and fermented milk formulas was determined in $2.1 \cdot 10^8$ dilution, in 11-18.3% of patients - in $4.3 \cdot 10^9$, and in patients in the II group - in $3.7 \cdot 10^7$ (in 7-11.7% of children) and in 23-38.3% of cases in $2.6 \cdot 10^8$ dilutions. The effectiveness of Dufalac therapy in combination with fermented milk formulas was noted in the normalization of stool softness, improvement of the baby's condition within a short time.

Conclusions. Thus, complex treatment of children with irritable bowel syndrome, accompanied by intestinal dysbiosis and constipation, should begin with the use of the prebiotic Dufalac in combination with fermented milk mixtures, which help restore the intestinal microbiota and gastrointestinal tract functions.

References /Список литературы/ Iqtiboslar

1. Ардатская М.Д. и др. Дисбиоз (дисбактериоз) кишечника: современное состояние проблемы, комплексная диагностика и лечебная коррекция //Экспериментальная и клиническая гастроэнтерология, 2015. № 5 (117).
2. Бактериологическая диагностика дисбактериоза: методические рекомендации для врачей-курсантов. - Казань, 2009. - 32 с.
3. Pulatova, N., & Ibragimova, M. (2024). YANGI TUG 'ILGAN CHAQALOQLARDA TUG'MA YURAK NUQSONLARINI RIVOJLANISHDAGI XAVF OMILLARINING AHAMIYATI. *Молодые ученые*, 2(7), 98-99.
4. Бычкова Н.К., Пикаревская И.В. Дисфункции желудочно-кишечного тракта у детей первого года жизни по данным мониторинга. *Сибирский журнал гастроэнтерологии и гепатологии*. — 2012 – С. 33 – 34.
5. Ibragimova, M., Shavazi, N., Lim, M., & Atayeva, M. (2022). Diagnostic and therapeutic methods for community-acquired pneumonia with atypical etiology in children. *Journal of Physician's Bulletin*, 1(4), 101.
6. Закирова Б.И., Турсунова Б.А., Улугова Х.Т. Взаимосвязь нарушения кишечной микробиоты и эндотоксемии у детей раннего возраста при осложненной пневмонии //Вестник экстренной медицины, 2013. № 3.
7. Shavkatova, Z. S. K., & Ibragimova, M. F. (2024). Changes in the Cytokine Profile in Mycoplasma Pneumonia in Children. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences*, 2(8), 99-101.
8. Шавази, Н., & Ибрагимова, М. (2023). Эффективность применения джозамицина при атипичных пневмониях у детей раннего возраста. *Международный журнал научной педиатрии*, 2(2), 44-46.
9. Скворцова В.А., Яцык Г.В. Звонкова Н.Г., Грибакин С. Г., Боровик Т. Э. Функциональные нарушения желудочно-кишечного тракта у детей грудного возраста: роль диетотерапии // Лечащий врач. – 2011. – № 6.
10. Мухаммадиев, И. С., Рахронов, Р. Н., & Ибрагимова, М. Ф. (2024). Эффективность применения кларитромицина при пневмонии с атипичной этиологией у детей. *Golden Brain*, 2(3), 110-115.
11. Шавази Н.М., Закирова Б.И., Алланазаров А.Б. Турсунова Б.А., Азимова Ш.Т. Острый обструктивный бронхит у детей: взаимосвязь микробиологии кишечника с клинико-лабораторной характеристикой. *Международ. Науч.практ.конф. "Тенденции и перспективы развития науки и образования в условиях глобализации"* выпуск 41. Сб. научных трудов Переяслав- Хмельницкий. 2018 г. С.706-708.
12. Akman I., Kuscu K., Ozdemir N., et al. Mothers' postpartum psychological adjustment and infantile colic // *Arch. Dis. Child*. 2006. May. №91(5). P. 417-419.
13. Lindberg T. Infantile colic and small intestinal function: a nutritional problem? *Acta. Paediatr. Suppl.* 1999. №430. P. 58-60.

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